

1 Design and development of a vaccine to eradicate childhood ear infection (otitis media).

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6 1. Hib (Haemophilus influenzae)

7 a. Design considerations:

8 The current Hib vaccine targets the capsular components of the bacteria, the type B polysaccharide. Type B capsular polysaccharide polyribosylribitol phosphate is known as PRP. The Hib polysaccharide tetanus protein conjugate is known as PRP-T.

9 b. Current availability:

10 Of the three major agents causing otitis media, present day vaccination coverage is most adequate for Haemophilus influenzae. Type B Hib vaccination resulted in large increases of non-typable Hib in the community.

11 2. Streptococcus pneumonia

12 a. Design considerations: The 2000 vaccine formulation covered 7 major serotypes causing pneumococcal infection and invasive disease. Future vaccines will target antigens enriched in penicillin-resistant infections, caused by 5 of the 7 major serotypes covered in the vaccine.

13 b. Current availability: A pneumococcal conjugate vaccine was introduced for infants in the United States in 2000.

14 3. Moraxella catarrhalis

15 a. Design considerations: Candidate antigens include Hemagglutinins, ubiquitous surface protein A; Lactoferrin binding protein A (LbpA) and lactoferrin binding protein B (LbpB), the transferrin binding protein A (TbpA) and transferrin binding protein B (TbpB), the CD and E porins, and the Catarrhalis outer membrane protein B (CopB). Lipooligosaccharide (LOS) and the ubiquitous surface protein A2 (UspA2). Other candidates include antigens of unknown function, such as the 200K protein.

16 b. Current availability: This vaccine is not currently available.

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